

Estimating Entropy of High Energy Single Particle Wavefunctions

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There has been interest (1) (2) in calculating high energy single particle wavefunction entropies using Shannon's entropy for momentum and space. These calculations are usually quite lengthy. In this note, we use the correspondence principle and the classical spatial density $C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity to estimate the high energy entropy. Such an approach seems to yield dependence on n , the energy level. We focus on the harmonic oscillator and particle in a box with no potential.

High Energy Wavefunctions and Entropy for the Harmonic Oscillator

In (1), a lengthy calculation of the entropy of oscillator wavefunctions, namely Hermite polynomials, is performed for both momentum and spatial Shannon's entropy. Here, spatial entropy is given by:

$$S_x = -\int dx W(x)W(x) \ln [W(x)W(x)] \quad \text{where } W(x) \text{ is the wavefunction } ((1))$$

And

$$S_p = -\int dp f_p f_p \ln [f_p f_p] \quad ((2)) \text{ where both calculations are done in one dimension.}$$

In (1), the relationship $S_x + S_p \approx D (1 + \ln(3.14))$ ((3)) where D =the number of dimensions is quoted. For the oscillator at high energy levels i.e. n approaching infinity S_x+S_p becomes very large and so ((3)) is not really relevant. It is relevant, however, for $n=0$.

After lengthy calculations, it is shown in (1) that:

$$S_x + S_p = \ln(n) - 2 - \ln(2) + 2\ln(3.14) + O(1) \quad ((4)) \text{ for the oscillator}$$

For large n , i.e. n approaching infinity, one has $S_x + S_p = \ln(n)$. ((4))

Estimation Approach for High Energy Entropy

In classical physics, one may use $C/v(x)$ as the spatial density (3). This is obtained from $dt=dx/v(x)$ where dt , the amount of time spent in a small region dx , is considered the probability. The velocity is found from $.5m v(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$. Thus, one may readily calculate classical spatial entropy:

$$S_x \text{ classical} = - \int dx C/v(x) \ln[C/v(x)] \quad ((5))$$

This is of the form of an area so $S_x \text{ classical} = L$ [Average entropy density value] ((5.5)).

Here L is the length of the one dimensional interval.

Consider the quantum mechanical oscillator problem. One has a Hermite polynomial of order n as the wavefunction and as n approaches infinity, the peaks of this highly oscillatory polynomial density $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ approach $C/v(x)$. Thus, it seems one may estimate entropy by considering a single oscillatory "hump". Its base value is dx and its peak value $C/v(x)$, and so we estimate the area by:

$$\text{Estimated Area of a hump} = - \{C/v(x) \ln[C/v(x)]\} \text{ average } dx \text{ b where } .5 < b < 1. \quad ((6))$$

The parameter b represents the fraction of the area of rectangle with base dx and height $C/v(x) \ln[C/v(x)]$ which is occupied by the hump. We assume a lower bound of $.5$ for b as an estimate. The hump density $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ is 0 at each end of dx . The $\{ \}$ average quantity is given in ((5)) and ((5.5)). Thus, the quantum spatial entropy is estimated as:

$$S_x \text{ quantum estimate} = [\text{Number of humps}] [\text{Est area of a hump}] \text{ with } dx=L/\text{number of humps}$$

Thus:

$$S_x \text{ quantum est} = - \{C/v(x) \ln[C/v(x)]\} \text{ average } L \text{ b } S_x \text{ classical } (1/L) \quad ((7))$$

Thus, it seems one may estimate quantum spatial entropy using classical density $C/v(x)$ and multiply the result by b (between $.5$ and 1).

$$\text{For the oscillator } .5m v(x)v(x) + .5 k x^*x = E.$$

$$S_x \text{ classical} = - \int dx C/v(x) \{ \ln(C) - \ln(v(x)) \} = -\ln(C) + C \int dx \ln(v)/v \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{Now } C \int dx/v(x) = 1 \text{ so } 1/C = \int dx / \sqrt{E-.5kx^*x}$$

One may use $\sqrt{.5k} x = \sqrt{E} \sin(a)$ and integrate from $a=0$ to $a=3.14/2$.

Thus, C is not dependent on $E=\hbar w(n+.5)$ and so is independent of n . Here we are interested in n approaching infinity and so are interested in the second term of ((8)).

$$\sqrt{.5m} v = \sqrt{E-.5kx^*x} = \sqrt{E} \cos(a) \text{ and } dx \sqrt{.5k} = \sqrt{E} \cos(a) da$$

Thus, the second term in ((8)) becomes:

$$C \sqrt{.5m} \int [\ln\{\sqrt{E/.5m}\} + \ln(\cos(a))] da \quad ((9))$$

Thus: S_x classical is of the order = $C \sqrt{.5m} 3.14/2 \ln\{\sqrt{E/.5m}\}$ ((10))

The large n dependence of ((10)) is $\ln(E)$ proportional to $\ln(n)$ which is the dependence obtained in (1). To obtain the factor in front of $\ln(n)$, one needs to evaluate the integral associated with C and estimate b (perhaps about .5 or so). Nevertheless, the approach presented here yields a quick estimate of S_x quantum for high n .

It is interesting to note that: $\ln(n)$ is related to the number of zeroes of a random polynomial (4). In particular, the number of zeroes is: $1 + 2/(3.14) \ln(n)$.

Thus, S_x for the quantum oscillator seems to be related to resolution, but this does not always hold. For example, later it will be seen that a similar result does not hold for S_x quantum for a particle in a box even though for large n , $\sin(6.28n/L)$ has high resolution.

In the case of momentum, one may use: $F = dp/dt$ or $dt = dp / (-d/dx V(x))$. For the case of the oscillator $F = -kx$ or $F = -k \sqrt{2/k} \sqrt{E - p^2/2m}$. Thus,

$$dt = \text{momentum density} = dp / [-k \sqrt{2/k} \sqrt{E - p^2/2m}]$$

This is of the same form as the spatial density except x is now p and some coefficients are changed. Thus, one may perform a similar integral for the oscillator and should again find a $\ln(n)$ dependence.

Thus : S_x quantum + S_p quantum is of the order of $\ln(n)$ ((11)) as shown in (1).

In this note, we do not calculate the coefficient in front of $\ln(n)$ as we wish to demonstrate that this method may be used to estimate high energy entropies.

Case of a Particle in a Box with no Potential

The case of a particle in a box is different, but we argue the same approach may be used. In (2) it is stated that

$$S_x \text{ quantum box } (n, L) = \ln(2L) - 1 \quad ((12))$$

Here n is the energy level and $W(x) = C \sin(6.28n/L x)$. Thus, as n becomes very large, one has a high frequency sine wave, but spatial entropy does not depend on n .

Consider the approach of using classical entropy to see if the same result holds. The spatial density should be $C/v(x)$ or Cm/p where $p = 6.28n/L$, using the result for a quantum particle in a box. Thus:

$$Cm / 6.28n L = 1 \quad C \text{ is of order } n \quad ((13))$$

$$S_x \text{ classical} = -\ln(C) + C \int dx \ln(v)/v = -\ln(C) + C \text{ Order}[\ln(n)/n]$$

Thus, with $C/v=1/L$, the large n terms of S_x classical are:

$-\ln(n) + \ln(n) = 0$. In other words, there is no n dependence. In (2), this lack of n dependence is called remarkable. In this note, we try to use the comparison with S_x classical to estimate S_x quantum and determine this result with minimal calculation for high n .

Extra Entropy Term

In the literature, a focus has been placed on calculating $S_x + S_p$, i.e. the Shannon's spatial and momentum entropies. In a previous note, we suggested using a quasiparticle probability when calculating Shannon's entropy, namely $W(x) \propto \exp(ipx)$. This leads to an overall entropy of $S_x + S_p + \int W(x) \times d/dx W(x)$. The last integral, however, integrates to -0.5 and so contributes nothing to large n results.

Thermodynamic Considerations

Given that one may estimate $S_x + S_p$ for quantum mechanical systems at high n , we try to determine whether such a value is useful in a thermodynamic equation such as:

$dE = T dS - (dE/dq) dq$ ((15)) where dq is a parameter such as L the box length for a particle in a box or k the spring constant for an oscillator.

Here we consider the case of the oscillator for which $E = \hbar \sqrt{k/m} (n + 0.5)$. We are only interested in high n . $T = dE/dS$ holding the spring constant fixed so $1/T = (1/\sqrt{k/m}) 1/n$ or T is of the order of n . We hold T fixed so even if one jumps from n to $n+1$ T does not really change. Entropy for the oscillator is proportional to $\ln(n)$, in fact, according to (1) it is exactly $-\ln(n)$. Thus, if $dq = dk = 0$, then $dE = \sqrt{k/m}$ and $TdS = n (1/n) \sqrt{k/m}$. Thus, thermodynamics appears to hold for large n in the quantum oscillator case. Here one is jumping from one n level to the next $n+1$ level. This result holds because

$dE = dE/dn dn = dE/dS dS/dn dn$ with $dn=1$ so it is not really clear that any statement is being made other than one of the chain rule of calculus.

(A full change in dE would involve jumping from n to $n+1$ and changing the value of the spring constant k , hence the two terms in ((15)).)

For the case of a particle in a box, matters are different. Entropy does not depend on n where $p = 6.28n/L$, but on L . L is usually an external parameter and so should be held constant when changing entropy. Thus, if one calculates $1/T = dS/dE$ with L constant, then one is making use of E proportional to $n^2/(L^2)$. There is no n dependence in S so $1/T=0$ which is problematic.

Thus, it is not clear how the thermodynamical equation ((15)) applies to a quantum particle in a box.

Conclusion

There has been interest in the literature in calculating Shannon's momentum and spatial entropy for different quantum potentials $V(x)$. In particular, attention has been paid to dependence on a parameter n which characterizes the energy level and especially to large n values. In this note, we present an estimation method which uses the classical $C/v(x)$ and an analogous expression for momentum density to calculate classical momentum and spatial densities. We then argue that these, when multiplied by $0 < b < 1$ (probably $.5 < b < 1$) are a good estimate for high n quantum entropies.

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